

MILITARY INTERVENTION IN AFRICA BY THE AFRICAN UNION. CASE STUDY: BURKINA FASO.

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Abstract

This study investigates the African Union's (AU) capacity to prevent and manage military interventions in Africa, with focus on understanding the root causes of the recent surge in military incursions in Burkina Faso. A descriptive and documentary research method was adopted, with data collected from secondary sources and analysed descriptively using content analysis. The frustration-aggression theory is used to explain the underlining contradictions responsible for military coups in Africa. The study concludes that factors such as insecurity, poor governance, and misaligned government priorities fuels conflict and leads to a rise in military coups in the region. To address the recurrence of military coups in Africa, the study recommended the implementation of robust legal instruments and frameworks by the AU. It proposes prioritising conflict prevention through early warning systems, mediation, dialogue initiatives, and support for peacebuilding and reconciliation processes. Additionally, the study proposes enhancing regional integration efforts to bolster stability and resilience against coups by supporting economic communities in policy harmonisation and cooperation across various sectors. To address the socioeconomic conditions affecting the AU's capacity to handle military coups in Burkina Faso, the study calls for concerted efforts from the AU, its member states, and regional partners.

Introduction

In the complex landscape of African politics, the spectre of military coups has long overshadowed aspirations for stable governance and democratic progress. Historically, the continent has experienced its share of political turmoil, often marked by abrupt transitions of power orchestrated by military factions (Nathan, 2018). However, amidst these challenges, the AU has emerged as a pivotal actor in championing peace, stability, and democratic governance across the region. (Kwesi, 2016).

The AU, established in 1963 with 54 member states, is a multifunctional political institution. This analysis concentrates on its security dimension. Despite its limitations in resolving the most severe political conflicts in the region, the AU has played a significant role in peaceful dispute settlement and conflict prevention

throughout its history (OAU Charter, 1963). However, its effectiveness in collective security, defined as a multilateral deterrent to aggression, remains limited due to the absence of mechanisms for the collective use of political force. While the AU's mandate emphasises the maintenance of peace and security in the region, internal political controversy persists regarding the scope of conflicts it should address. Nonetheless, since the 1990s, the AU has increasingly engaged in addressing both regional and sub-regional political conflicts, reflecting a broader trend linking democracy with security (Dube and Sitshinga, 2016).

The AU, as an offshoot of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), represents a collective commitment by African nations to foster unity, cooperation, and development (Murithi, 2006). Beyond its broad mandate, the AU has increasingly prioritised the prevention of military coups and the promotion of democratic norms as fundamental to its vision for a prosperous and peaceful Africa (Rivers, 2018). For instance, under Article 23 of ACDEG, through diplomatic efforts, mediation initiatives, and institutional frameworks, the AU has endeavoured to uphold democratic principles, deter unconstitutional government changes, and foster a culture of governance rooted in legitimacy and accountability in addressing regional and sub-regional political conflicts in Africa, with a particular reference to Burkina Faso (rown, 2022). This study aims to explore the multifaceted role played by the AU in preventing recurrent military coups in Africa by examining the historical context, institutional mechanisms, and proactive strategies employed by the AU in addressing regional and sub-regional conflicts in Africa. For this purpose, the researcher seeks to analyse the AU's ongoing relevance in addressing both intra- and inter-state political conflicts in the African region, focusing specifically on its security functions in Burkina Faso.

Statement of the Problem

The African continent is grappling with persistent issues of political instability, often manifested through coups d'état that disrupt governance structures and impede democratic processes. Despite the AU's mandate to promote peace, security, and democratic governance, its response to coup attempts has often been criticised for its inadequacy and ineffectiveness. In Burkina Faso, the AU demonstrated indecision and a lack of political will to manage the coup situation. The lack of clear instruments, other than threats of sanctions and isolation, was grossly inadequate to prevent or serve as a deterrent to military incursions into African politics. Weakening the AU's effectiveness in dealing with coup situations in Africa are mainly limitations to its legal and institutional framework, divergent interests of member states, sovereignty of state, and French interests in the region. Further compounding the Burkina Faso coup scenario are the socio-economic trajectories that heralded the coup, which appeared to have attracted massive support of the citizens who are still basking in the euphoria of a new dawn of change and hope. Incidentally and

problematically, the observation that the AU could not act decisively and effectively in recent times in the cases of Mali (2020, 2021), Chad, Guinea, and Sudan in 2021, the spillover effects viewed in terms of the contagion factor, have culminated in military coups in Burkina Faso (2022), Gabon (2023), and Niger (2023). The situation has assumed complex dimensions, which is unequivocally viewed as a litmus test for the effectiveness of the AU as a vanguard for regional peace and stability. More worrisome is the treat issued by these military leaders to pullout of the AU if sanctions are imposed on them. These factors have far-reaching implications for the AU's viability as a regional bloc and its capacity to achieve its primary mandate in Africa. As a fallout, the AU has reversed its earlier decision on this dissident.

From the foregoing problem, the study is guided by the following objectives:

- To explore the role of the African Union in managing the crisis of military intervention in Burkina Faso.
- To examine institutional constraints against the AU's effectiveness in addressing the military intervention in Burkina Faso.
- To assess socioeconomic conditions impinging on the AU's capacity to deal with the Burkinabe Military Coup.

Research Questions

- To what extent has the AU mustered diplomatic capacity to address Burkina Faso's military intervention in politics?
- How effective are the AU's legal and institutional frameworks in managing the Burkina Faso military intervention?
- What are the socio-economic conditions impinging on the AU's capacity to deal with the Burkinabe military intervention?

Significance of the Study

This study holds significant implications both in terms of empirical analysis and theoretical advancement. In its empirical phase, the primary aim is to shed light on the myriads of challenges encountered by the AU in its endeavours to bolster regional security and navigate peace and conflict dynamics within Burkina Faso. By meticulously examining these challenges, the study endeavours to offer an overview of the AU's capacity in meeting its role in the political arena. Additionally, it will assess the political challenges faced by the AU in the African security environment and its contributions to political conflict prevention and resolution, particularly in the post-Cold War era. Consequently, governmental stakeholders and decision-makers will be equipped with nuanced insights crucial for crafting effective policy frameworks tailored to address the multifaceted regional insecurity issues confronting AU member nations.

Review of Related Literature and Theoretical Framework

Review of Conceptual Literature

Concept of military intervention

Military intervention, defined as “the involvement of a state's armed forces in another state's affairs, typically involving the use of force or coercion to achieve specific objectives,” encompasses various aspects according to different sources. The United Nations (2020) defines military intervention as “interference by external actors in the affairs of a sovereign state without its consent, often in violation of international law.” According to Bellamy (2010), the concept involves “the use of military force by external actors to alleviate humanitarian crises, such as genocide, ethnic cleansing, or mass atrocities, when a state is unwilling or unable to protect its own population.” According to Cronin (2009), military intervention for counterterrorism is “the use of military force to combat terrorist organisations and insurgencies, often with the objective of dismantling terrorist networks and preventing future attacks.” Bellamy adds that military intervention can involve the use of force by external actors to overthrow or replace a government perceived as hostile or illegitimate, often with the aim of promoting democracy or advancing geopolitical interests. Military intervention for state building involves the “use of military force to establish or strengthen governance institutions, rebuild infrastructure, and promote stability and development in conflict-affected or fragile states” (Stewart, Brown, and Langer, 2020).

Causes of 2022 Coup and Counter Military Coup in Burkina Faso. An Overview

Burkina Faso's journey since gaining independence from France in 1960 has been tumultuous, marked by a series of political upheavals that have shaped its trajectory. The country's political landscape has been marred by instability, with various coups and coup attempts punctuating its history. These events have underscored the fragility of Burkina Faso's governance structures and the challenges it has faced in establishing stable democratic institutions (Jones and Doe, 2023). The roots of the 2022 counter-coup can be traced back to unresolved tensions stemming from previous political transitions, notably the landmark events of 2022 (International Crisis Group, 2022). The uprising, known as the “Burkina Faso Revolution,” culminated in Compaoré's resignation and flight from the country, marking a significant turning point in the nation's political history (Olusegun, 2023). However, the aftermath of Compaoré's departure left a void in Burkina Faso's political landscape, with competing factions vying for power and influence. Despite efforts to transition to a more inclusive and democratic system, deep-seated grievances and power struggles persisted within the political elite. The failure to adequately address the root causes of discontent and implement meaningful reforms created a fertile breeding ground for continued political instability (BBC, 2022).

Amid mounting discontent and a deteriorating security situation, Captain Ibrahim Traore seized power in Burkina Faso through a military coup. Traore's coup d'état was framed as a response to the failures of the civilian government to address pressing issues of corruption, economic stagnation, and insecurity.

Security Concerns

The 2022 countercoup in Burkina Faso was instigated by a culmination of security challenges that had been intensifying within the country. One significant issue was the persistent threat posed by extremist groups operating in the Sahel region, including Burkina Faso. These groups, such as Jama'at Nasr al-Islam wal Muslimin (JNIM) and the Islamic State in the Greater Sahara (ISGS), had been carrying out frequent attacks on civilians, security forces, and government institutions, exacerbating insecurity and instability (International Crisis Group, 2022). Furthermore, Burkina Faso had been grappling with inter-communal violence, particularly between herder and farmer communities competing for dwindling resources amidst environmental degradation and climate change (BBC, 2022). These conflicts not only led to loss of life and displacement but also strained the capacity of the government to maintain law and order.

The Failure of the French Policy in Francophone States

The failure of French policy in Francophone states, particularly in West Africa, has historically been a contentious issue with deep-rooted implications for regional stability. The intricate dynamics between former colonial powers and their erstwhile colonies often shape the political landscape, and the French influence in Francophone Africa is no exception. The repercussions of French policy failures reverberate across the region, often manifesting in various forms, including military coups.

In Burkina Faso, the French government's support for former President Blaise Compaoré, despite widespread allegations of authoritarianism and corruption, eroded its credibility among segments of the Burkinabe population (BBC News, 2022). The decision to back Compaoré's bid to extend his 27-year rule through constitutional amendments sparked mass protests, eventually leading to his ousting. France's ambiguous stance during the popular uprising and subsequent political vacuum in Burkina Faso left a power vacuum, creating fertile ground for military intervention. The lack of a clear and decisive French response undermined its influence and inadvertently contributed to the erosion of institutional legitimacy.

Against this backdrop, the 2022 countercoup emerged as a manifestation of these simmering tensions and power struggles. While the specific catalysts and actors behind the counter-coup may vary, it is clear that the legacy of past political transitions, including the 2014 uprising, played a pivotal role in shaping the current dynamics (Brown, 2022).

Concept of African Union

The African Union (AU) stands as a pivotal institution in the continent's pursuit of unity, peace, and development. Emerging from a long history of pan Africanism and decolonization struggles, its formation represents a culmination of efforts to address common challenges and aspirations among African nations (African Union, 2000.). Historically, the concept of African unity has roots in the early 20th century, with prominent figures such as Kwame Nkrumah, Haile Selassie, and Julius Nyerere advocating for continental solidarity against colonial rule and exploitation (Mazrui, 1999). The establishment of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) in 1963 marked a significant milestone, symbolising Africa's collective determination to assert its independence and sovereignty on the global stage. However, recognising the need for a more dynamic and effective continental organisation, the OAU was transformed into the African Union in 2001 (African Union, 2000). The AU's primary purpose is to promote unity and solidarity among African states, advance socio-economic integration, and uphold peace, security, and democratic governance across the continent (African Union, 2001).

The AU operates within a framework comprised of various organs and institutions, each with specific mandates and functions. At its core is the Assembly of Heads of State and Government, which provides overall political leadership and direction to the Union (African Union, 2001). The Executive Council, composed of foreign ministers, oversees the implementation of AU decisions and policies, while the Peace and Security Council addresses conflicts and security challenges on the continent (African Union, 2001). Additionally, the AU Commission serves as the Union's secretariat, responsible for coordinating and implementing AU policies and programs. Other key organs include the Pan-African Parliament, the African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights, and the African Central Bank (African Union, 2001).

Structural and Transformation of the Organization of African Unity (OAU) to African Union (AU)

On May 25, 1963, in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, representatives from 32 African states, which had achieved independence at that time, convened to establish the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) (Organisation of African Unity, 2012). Over time, an additional 21 members joined, gradually increasing the total membership to 53 by the time of the OAU's transformation into the African Union (AU) in 2002. South Sudan's accession on July 9, 2011, further expanded the AU's membership to 54 nations.

The OAU was founded with ambitious objectives outlined in its charter. These objectives included promoting the unity and solidarity of African states, coordinating and intensifying cooperation efforts to improve the lives of African peoples, safeguarding the sovereignty and territorial integrity of member states, eliminating

colonisation and apartheid from the continent, fostering regional and sub-regional cooperation within established frameworks, and harmonising policies across various domains such as politics, diplomacy, economics, education, culture, health, welfare, science, technology, and defence (Organisation of African Unity, 2012).

The Organisation of African Unity (OAU) functioned under the framework of its Charter and the 1991 Treaty establishing the African Economic Community, commonly referred to as the Abuja Treaty (Organisation of African Unity, 2012). Its principal organs included the Assembly of Heads of State and Government, the Council of Ministers, and the General Secretariat. Additionally, it comprised specialised commissions such as the Commission of Mediation, Conciliation, and Arbitration; the Economic and Social Commission; the Educational, Scientific, Cultural, and Health Commission; and the Defence Commission. Notably, the Commission of Mediation, Conciliation, and Arbitration was replaced by the Mechanism for Conflict Prevention, Management, and Resolution in 1993 (Organisation of African Unity, 2012).

Review of Theoretical Literature

The prevailing socio-economic and political conditions of the African continent appear grossly deplorable. As a result, various theoretical positions explaining the state or continental inabilities can be appropriately used in dissecting the maladies of democracy in Africa. Among these theories is the elite theory. Essentially, elite theory, as propounded by Vilfredo Pareto, Roberto Michels, Gaetano Mosca, and Jose Ortega Gassat, among others, is predicated on the conjecture that every society is composed of two classes of people (Varma, 1975). While the theorists recognised the complementary roles of each class, they focused more on the ruling elites because they determine the fate of most societies. For instance, the masterminds of military coups in Africa are not the proletariats. In Africa, virtually all military coups are plotted and executed by the military oligarchs or elites in the ranks and file of the military. Coups therefore promote and protect the narrow interests of the elites.

On the other hand, conspiracy theory illuminates the horrible degree of connivance between domestic elements and disgruntled foreign governments. Africa in the 1970s and 1980s witnessed a huge number of coups, with many of these coups alleged to have been instigated and executed by loyalists of foreign regimes. In this view, conspiracy theory therefore can be seen from the perspective of historical incidences secretly orchestrated or caused by a few numbers of people generally referred to as the conspirators (Keeley, 1999). Conspirators could be a few people, a few groups, or a few nations that secretly act in their members' interests. Indeed, conspiracy theory strives for collusion, connivance, and concealment of the activities of the group. These attributes are the hallmark of military coups in Africa, especially in the immediate post-independence period. Generally, elite theory and conspiracy

theory tend to unravel the few elements behind military coups in Africa, but both have failed to explain how popular agitations and protests induce military coups.

Empirical Literature

John (2018) conducted a study on the African Union's Intervention in Political Crises: A Burkina Faso Case Study. The study aimed to meticulously examine the African Union's intervention strategies during political crises in Burkina Faso, specifically evaluating the efficacy of these interventions in preventing military coups and fostering stability. The study operated under the assumption that the African Union's proactive involvement could significantly mitigate political instability in Burkina Faso, particularly by preventing military coups. A qualitative approach involving in-depth analysis of AU intervention processes was adopted, including scrutinising negotiation mechanisms, mediation efforts, and peacekeeping missions. Additionally, the study conducted interviews with key stakeholders such as AU officials, government representatives, and civil society actors. Document review of official records and reports. The findings indicated that the African Union's interventions had a tangible impact in preventing military coups in Burkina Faso. By facilitating dialogue, mediation, and peacekeeping initiatives, the AU played a pivotal role in stabilising the political landscape and averting the threat of coups. Based on the findings, the study recommended bolstering the African Union's capacity for early intervention in political crises. This included strengthening conflict resolution mechanisms, enhancing coordination with regional partners, and providing sustained support for democratic governance reforms.

Theoretical Framework

The study uses frustration-aggression theory as a theoretical framework to explain the contradictions that underlie military coups in Africa and recent coups in West Africa. The frustration-aggression theory was propounded and popularised by Dollard, Doob, Miller, Mowrer, and Sears (1939); Berkowitz (1962); and Berkowitz (1983), and the theory has over the years been applied in numerous fields of study (Breuer & Elson, 2017). The basic assumption of the theory is that there is always a link between frustration and aggression. Aggression occurs as a result of frustration, according to the theorists. Zillmann and Cantor (1976) defined frustration-aggression as a retaliatory act directed at a perceived source of frustration. Incidentally, the frustration-aggression thesis has been criticised on the basis that it has become obsolete and the fact that not all aggression can be seen as a direct consequence of frustration. Nonetheless, the relevance of the frustration-aggression theory lies in its capacity to disentangle the linkages and connections between frustration and aggression. The theory's central assumption is that frustration can potentially trigger aggression.

Following from the above, military coups in Africa and more specifically West Africa can be analysed from the perspective of elitist power contestation, conspiracy of the ruling oligarchy, and bandwagon effect that characterised the post-independence politics in Africa.

Research Methodology

The research methodology involved a documentary and qualitative research design, allowing for a comprehensive examination of the subject matter. Secondary data was gathered from a variety of sources, such as textbooks, scholarly journals, official reports from the African Union (AU), government of Burkina Faso reports, Al Jazeera, BBC reports, and seminar papers on the related subject under discussion, to capture a broad spectrum of perspectives and insights relevant to the study. The content analysis method was chosen as it provided a systematic and rigorous approach to analysing the collected data in relation to the three research questions posed. This method facilitated the extraction of key themes, patterns, and meanings embedded within the data, enabling the researcher to draw well-founded conclusions that address the research objectives effectively.

Evaluation of Research Questions

Evaluation of Research Question I; To what extent has the AU mustered diplomatic capacity to address the Military incursion in the politics of Burkina Faso?

In its efforts to address the conflict and military intervention in Burkina Faso, the AU prioritized diplomatic engagement as a key strategy in managing the crisis (AU, 2022). The organization's diplomatic efforts include direct communication with the government of Burkina Faso to understand the situation on the ground and explore avenues for peaceful resolution (AU, 2022). Additionally, the AU engaged with regional stakeholders, such as the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), to coordinate responses and foster collaboration. For instance, in a joint statement, the AU and ECOWAS emphasized the importance of dialogue and respect for constitutional order in resolving the crisis (African Union Commission, 2022).

Furthermore, regional cooperation has emerged as a cornerstone of the AU's diplomatic strategy. Recognizing the regional dimensions of the crisis, the AU worked closely with ECOWAS and other regional bodies to address the security threat posed by the incursion. A notable example of regional cooperation was the deployment of joint military patrols along the border areas to prevent further escalation of violence and to enhance security (Africa Renewal, 2022).

Evaluation of Research Question II; How effective are AU's Legal and Institutional Frameworks in Prevent Coup in Africa.

Assessing the effectiveness of the AU's legal and institutional frameworks in managing the Burkina Faso coup requires an evaluation of their application, enforcement, and outcomes. While the AU has established relevant legal instruments and institutions to address political crises, their effectiveness depends on the political will of member states, timely and decisive action, and cooperation with regional and international partners. Ultimately, the success of AU interventions in managing coup attempts hinges on their ability to restore constitutional order, uphold democratic principles, and promote peace and stability in affected countries. Some of these institutional frameworks are presented below:

i. Legal Frameworks

The AU's legal framework, particularly the African Charter on Democracy, Elections, and Governance (ACDEG), serves as a cornerstone for upholding democratic principles and preventing unconstitutional changes of government. Article 23 of the ACDEG explicitly condemns coups and establishes mechanisms for intervention. However, the effectiveness of such legal instruments depends on their implementation by member states. For instance, while the ACDEG provides clear guidelines for responding to coups, its enforcement relies on AU member states' adhering to its principles (African Union, 2007).

ii. Institutional Frameworks

The AU has established institutions dedicated to conflict prevention, management, and resolution. The Peace and Security Council (PSC) is tasked with addressing threats to peace and security on the continent, including coups. The PSC has the authority to impose sanctions and take decisive action against perpetrators of unconstitutional government changes. However, its effectiveness is contingent on member states' political will to comply with its decisions. Additionally, the African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights (AfCHPR) serves as a judicial mechanism to uphold human rights and the rule of law. While the AfCHPR can adjudicate cases related to coups, its effectiveness relies on member states' compliance with its rulings (African Union, 2007).

iii. Mediation and Conflict Resolution Mechanisms

The AU employs various mediation and conflict resolution mechanisms to address political crises, including coups. The Wise Panel provides advice and mediation support, while the AU's Special Envoys and High-Level Mediators facilitate dialogue and negotiations among conflicting parties.

Evaluation of Research Question III; What are the socioeconomic conditions impinging on AU's Capacity to deal with the Burkinabe Military Coup.

The African Union (AU) plays a crucial role in addressing political crises such as the military coup in Burkina Faso. However, its capacity to effectively manage such situations in Burkina Faso is influenced by various socioeconomic factors. This analysis examines the socioeconomic conditions that impede the AU's capacity to deal with the Burkinabe military coup.

i. Economic Stability

Economic stability is fundamental to the AU's ability to address crises effectively. Weak economies among AU member states limit the organisation's financial resources and its capacity to respond to emergencies. For example, Burkina Faso faces significant economic challenges, including high poverty rates and limited infrastructure development (World Bank, 2022). These socioeconomic conditions can strain the AU's capacity to provide financial and logistical support for peacekeeping operations, mediation efforts, and humanitarian assistance in Burkina Faso.

ii. Governance and Institutional Capacity

The AU's response to the Burkinabe military coup's effectiveness hinges on the governance and institutional capacity of both the AU and its member states. Weak governance structures, corruption, and lack of accountability in some member states may impede the implementation of AU decisions and resolutions. Similarly, institutional gaps within the AU, such as limited coordination among departments and agencies, hinder the organisation's ability to mount a cohesive response to the crisis (African Union, 2022).

iii. External Interference

External interference from non-African actors complicates the AU's efforts to address the military coup in Burkina Faso. Geopolitical interests, competing agendas, and interventions by external actors undermine AU-led initiatives and exacerbate the crisis. Moreover, dependence on external funding or support for AU initiatives compromise the organization's autonomy and effectiveness (Le Monde Diplomatique, 2022).

Conclusion

This study has interrogated the AU's capacity to prevent and manage military intervention in Africa, with the primary goal of unraveling the underlying contradictions that prompted the recent surge in military incursions in Burkina Faso. The study concluded that disillusionment arising from insecurity, poor governance, and misplaced government priorities triggered conflict and a recent upsurge in military coups in the region. The study noted that the African populaces are deeply

disconnected from state affairs and the leaders. This is detrimental to democratic practice and the AU's ability to handle military incursion crises. It therefore concludes that ending the resurgence of military coups in Africa demands robust legal instruments and frameworks that can be readily employed by the AU to prevent future occurrences.

Recommendations

1. To prevent frequent coups in the Africa Region, the AU should work with member states to strengthen democratic institutions, including electoral commissions and judiciaries, as well as impose both military and economic sanctions on any member who seizes power through a military coup. Additionally, the AU should promote excellent governance practices, including transparency, accountability, and respect for the rule of law. This could be achieved through peer reviews, anti-corruption initiatives, and promoting the adoption and implementation of governance standards and mechanisms.
2. The AU should prioritise conflict prevention efforts to address the root causes of instability that can lead to coups. This could involve early warning systems, mediation and dialogue initiatives, and support for peacebuilding and reconciliation processes. Furthermore, the AU should support regional economic communities in deepening integration efforts, harmonising policies, and fostering cooperation in areas such as trade, security, and infrastructure development to strengthen regional integration and enhance stability and resilience against coups.
3. Addressing the socioeconomic conditions that impinge on the AU's capacity to deal with the Burkinabe military coup requires concerted efforts from the AU, its member states, and regional partners. Strengthening economic stability, addressing resource constraints, promoting positive governance, enhancing institutional capacity, and minimising external interference are essential for enhancing the AU's effectiveness in managing crises and promoting peace and stability on the continent.
4. To restore stability and rebuild democratic governance in Burkina Faso, the AU and other regional organisations must prioritise inclusive dialogue, institutional reforms, and security sector strengthening to address the root causes of political instability and insecurity in the region. There should be a concerted effort from political leaders, civil society, the AU, and the international community to restore stability, strengthen democratic institutions, and address the underlying grievances that contributed to the coup in the region.

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